

THE PRODUCT IS OF QUALITY MANUFACTURE LOCATION OF METROLOGICAL SUPPLY.

Badalov Nomoz Joraboevich

Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute, Acting associate professor,
telephone: +998903110662 nomozbadalov@gmail.com

ANNOTATION: *To assess the description of the specified characteristics for product quality assessment, to have measurement information about product characteristics, to ensure high accuracy of measurement data, to ensure the guaranteed accuracy of measurement data of measuring instruments in production, to determine the terms of use and all organizational-regulatory and legal issues related to the problem of measurement the solution depends on the metrological supply system.*

Keywords: *product, standard, metrology, resources, certification, measurement, quality, management, quality system, validation, equipment, calibration, international standards, interchangeability, security, competition.*

Product quality management criteria Any management system has management criteria that determine its performance. Product quality is characterized by its ability to meet certain needs in accordance with its function. From the point of view of quality management, these characteristics can be considered as management criteria [1]. For example, if it is necessary to reduce the consumption of materials, the mass of the machine is taken as a criterion. If it is necessary to increase the reliability, as a criterion, the car will work without stalling, etc. The mentioned criteria belong to the type of technical criteria and they are widely used [2]. But they are private criteria. They do not provide an estimate of the costs of achieving quality. Without them, the effectiveness of the product quality management system cannot be evaluated. Therefore, in quality management, it is necessary to use criteria that combine technical and economic characteristics of product quality. In this case, it is appropriate to use the concept of integral product quality. The integral quality of the product

is understood as the ratio of the sum of the use or consumption of the product to the sum of the costs of creating and using the useful product [3].

$$K_H = \frac{\mathfrak{D}}{3_c + 3_{\mathfrak{D}}}$$

Where: $\mathfrak{D}$ - is the benefit of the total use of the product;
 3_c - costs incurred to create the product;
 $3_{\mathfrak{D}}$ - costs of using the product.

The integral indicator of quality responds sensitively to both the increase in useful properties (*increase $\mathfrak{D}$*) and the change in costs (*increase $3_c + 3_{\mathfrak{D}}$*).

Generally, the integral indicator of quality increases over time, as the characteristics of the product improve due to technical improvement and modernization, and costs decrease due to the increase in productivity during the production and use of the product, but in practice, the increase of the integral indicator of quality is observed to stop or, in worse cases, decrease [4].

In such a case, the benefit from the improvement of the useful properties increases less than the corresponding costs, even though the useful properties do not change, and the costs increase due to the deterioration of production performance and product utilization. Naturally, the integral indicator of quality cannot be allowed to decrease. If this happens, it will be necessary to raise the technology to a higher level, which will ensure the production of modernized or new products, which will fully satisfy the needs of the consumer, using less labor, material and energy for production. In this case, the integral indicator of quality also begins to rise upwards [5].

Metrological assurance of product quality, as mentioned above, product quality is a set of features that provide the ability to meet certain needs in accordance with its function. In order to evaluate the quality of the product, it is necessary to evaluate the description of the specified properties, that is, it is necessary to have measurement information about the product properties [6]. The metrological supply system is tasked with ensuring the high accuracy of measurement data, creating the system and conditions for ensuring measurement unity in the country, providing guaranteed accuracy of measurement data of measuring instruments, determining the terms of use, and solving all organizational, regulatory and legal issues related to the measurement problem [7].

Metrological supply is a set of organizational and technical measures that ensure obtaining and using measurement information. Selection of characteristics to be evaluated during measurement, testing, and control of product quality, planning of measurement, testing, and control processes, development of measurement, testing, and control methods and metrological attestation, measurement, testing, and providing control processes with appropriate measuring tools, keeping measuring tools in metrologically correct condition, performing measurement, testing and control processes and processing their results, training and improving the qualifications of specialists related to obtaining and using measurement, testing and control results, as well as metrological support in the enterprise includes metrological examination of design, construction and technological documents in order to determine the compatibility of modern technical level and high-quality products for production [8].

Determination of the nomenclature of characteristics to be measured during control during metrological expertise, introduction of the optimal accuracy of the selected characteristics, assessment of the correctness of the selection of measuring instruments and determination of the correctness of the requirements for measurement methods, ensuring the given accuracy of measurement when using unified and automated measuring instruments, the main issues of determining the methods of measuring results, determining whether the units of measurement are used correctly, and analyzing the product from the point of view of suitability for control, i.e., the analysis of whether it is possible to measure its characteristics, are seen [9].

Metrological examination allows to eliminate metrological errors at the stages of development of construction documents and preparation of technological process. If these errors slip through and enter the aforementioned documents, the possibility of economic losses and losses from measurement and control errors increases [10]. At the international level, there is also an international organization that legislates in the field of metrology. The main goal of this organization is international coordination of state metrological services and activities of other national institutions. The main directions of activity of MOZM are to determine the unity of methodological and normative metrological characteristics of

measuring instruments for the countries that are members of MOZM, to harmonize comparison equipment, comparison methods, benchmarks, standard and working measuring instruments, to ensure the use of internationally unified measurement units in countries, to develop the most convenient forms of metrological services and to ensure the unity of the state instructions on their introduction, to provide scientific and technical assistance in the provision of metrological work in developing countries and to provide them with the necessary technical tools, uniform training of personnel at various levels in the field of metrology is to determine the rules [11].

"Metrology and metrological support" - the field of scientific, technical and normative-methodical foundations necessary to ensure the uniformity and required accuracy of measurements. The novelty and importance of the scientific and technical problems of this specialty for the national economy is the development of new measurement methods and tools and the improvement of the existing ones, the solution of new scientific-based organizational and methodological problems aimed at ensuring the unity of measurements and the required accuracy, as well as eliminating the negative consequences of unreliable measurement results and has been excluding. Products and technological processes, equipment of enterprises and testing laboratories, measuring, testing and inspection methods and tools, regulatory documents, systems of metrological assurance of scientific, production, social and environmental activities are considered objects of professional activity [12]. The Technical Regulatory Agency of Uzbekistan is the largest applied metrology organization whose main task is to ensure and maintain the uniformity of measurements in industry, health care, communication systems, trade, defense, resource accounting, nature protection and other economic activities. The main areas of metrological activity, comparison, calibration of measuring instruments, testing for type confirmation, metrological expertise and certification of test equipment and methods of measurement are carried out by metrological service [13]. The consistent increase of metrological potential makes it possible to master the types of comparison, calibration and testing of new measuring instruments on a regular basis. The correctness of mutual calculations between suppliers and consumers of fuel, heat, water is only possible in main

oil and gas pipelines, oil refineries, oil bases, oil and gas accounting nodes, heat and water supply systems, gas, water, heat, electricity and consumption of petroleum products can be guaranteed under the condition of efficient and independent metrological supply of measuring devices. Accounting of material wealth and energy resources is subject to state metrology inspection and control, and therefore all gas, cold and hot water and electricity metering devices are subject to state metrology inspection and control and must be subject to mandatory inspection based on the specified interval between comparisons [14].

Metrological supply measurement information is subject not only to quantity, but also to quality. This includes characteristics such as measurement accuracy, reliability, cost per unit and efficiency. All these quality descriptions are based on metrological assurance. Metrological supply can be defined as the determination and implementation of technical tools, procedures and rules, standards, scientific and organizational bases necessary to ensure the unity of measurements and to achieve the required accuracy. Based on this description, it can be said that the task of the metrological supply is to organize, ensure and implement the serviceability of measuring instruments, carry out measurements, develop and implement normative documents on processing and recommending its results, conducting expert examinations of documents, state testing of measuring instruments. , metrological certifications of measuring tools and methods are uploaded [15].

The four constituents of metrological supply are the scientific basis of metrology - the science of measurements, its technical basis - state standards of units of magnitude, transfer of units of magnitude from standards to working tools, creation and development of measuring tools, mandatory state tests of measuring tools and metrological attestation of their performance methods, measurement conducting a mandatory state comparison in the development, maintenance and use of tools, creation of standard samples on the composition and properties of substances and materials, standard references, mandatory state testing of products. The organizational basis is the metrological service of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which consists of the metrological service of the state and courts. Normative-legal

bases are relevant republican laws, state standards, state and industry regulatory documents [16].

In short, the metrological supply consists of improving product quality, production and automation efficiency, ensuring the interchangeability of details and aggregates, ensuring the reliability of accounting of material assets and energy resources, protecting the environment, and maintaining health. The level of metrological security directly affects the quality of the product [17]. In order to further increase the effectiveness of this effect, special importance is given to metrological preventive works and issues of metrological maintenance in production preparation. This will create a suitable basis for the deeper formation of market relations in our republic and the increase of export possibilities of manufactured products [18].

Fundamentals of metrological supply. The metrological supply system cooperates with the system of ensuring the State Unit of Measurements of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the State System of Standardization of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the field systems of standardization and certification. The mutual cooperation of the system with the systems of ensuring the unity of measurements of other countries and international bodies is regulated in accordance with the current legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the normative documents of the Agency for Communication and Informatization of Uzbekistan, and the Agency for Technical Regulation of Uzbekistan.

References:

1. O'g B. O. N. et al. The role of quality management system in increasing product quality in enterprises //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 228-233.
2. Бадалов Н. Ж., Бердимуродов Г. Т., Бадалов У. Н. СИФАТЛИ МАХСУЛОТ ИШЛАБ ЧИҚАРИЛИШИДА СИНОВ ВА ЎЛЧОВЛАРНИНГ АХАМИЯТИ //ИТМОИЙ ФАНЛАРДА INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 101-106.

3. Бадалов Н. Ж., Бадалов У. Н. КОРХОНАЛАРДА МАҲСУЛОТЛАР СИФАТИНИ БОШҚАРИШНИНГ АСОСИЙ ФУНКЦИЯЛАРИ //Academic research in modern science. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 38-45.
4. Juraboyevich B. N. et al. Development Of Metrology And The Role And Importance Of Metrological Supply In Enterprises //Eurasian Research Bulletin. – 2022. – Т. 4. – С. 136-139.
5. Juraboyevich B. N., Son B. O. N. THE ROLE OF QUALITY PRODUCTION IN ENTERPRISES //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 9. – №. 10. – С. 644-647.
6. Jo‘raboevich B. N., Ikramovich I. D., Nomozovich B. U. SINOV VA KALIBRLASH LABORATORIYALARIDA KOMPETENTLIGINI XALQARO DARAJADA OSHIRISH OMILLARI //E Conference Zone. – 2022. – С. 128-131.
7. Бадалов Н. Ж., Икромов Д. И., Бадалов У. Н. КОРХОНАЛАРДА ЎЛЧАШЛАР, СИНОВЛАР ВА ТАҲЛИЛЛАРНИНГ МЕТРОЛОГИК АХАМИЯТИ //Международная конференция академических наук. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 15. – С. 11-17.
8. Jo‘raboevich B. N., Ikramovich I. D., Nomozovich B. U. SIFAT MENEJMENT TIZIMINING-SINOV VA KALIBRLASH LABORATORIYALARIDAGI O‘RNI //E Conference Zone. – 2022. – С. 67-71.
9. BADALOV U. N. O. QUALITY IN PRODUCT QUALITY MANAGEMENT SIGNIFICANCE OF INDICATORS //INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE" INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION". – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 65-75.
10. BADALOV U. N. O. THE IMPORTANCE OF TESTING LABORATORIES AND THEIR ACCREDITATION //INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE" INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION". – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 163-169.
11. Juraboevich B. N. Products in Manufacturing Enterprises the Essence of Quality Management //International Journal of Development and Public Policy. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 117-118.

- 12.**Jo‘raboevich B. N. QUALITY EXPORT PRODUCTS IN ENTERPRISES GENERAL AND SPECIAL IN PRODUCTION IMPORTANCE OF REGULATIONS //ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 6. – C. 1-7.
- 13.**Jo‘raboyevich B. N. ROLE OF COMPARISON, CALIBRATION AND METROLOGICAL CERTIFICATION IN ENTERPRISES //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 10. – C. 168-175.
- 14.**BADALOV N. J., RUSTAMOV N. T. THE ROLE OF MANAGEMENT IN ENTERPRISES THAT HAVE IMPLEMENTED A QUALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM //International Academic Research Journal Impact Factor 7.4. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 1. – C. 46-55.
- 15.**Badalov N. J. MANAGE PRODUCT QUALITY IN ENTERPRISES CONTENT //INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE" INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION". – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 2. – C. 58-64.
- 16.**Jo‘raboevich B. N., Abduraxmonovich S. H. M. KORXONALARDA O ‘LCHASH VOSITALARNI SINOVDAN O ‘TKAZISHDA METROLOGIK XIZMATINING O ‘RNI //Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 701-704.
- 17.**BADALOV N. J. O. R. THE SIGNIFICANCE OF CERTIFICATION IN ENTERPRISES WITH A QUALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM //INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE" INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION". – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 2. – C. 146-156.
- 18.**SHERTAYLAKOV G. M., BADALOV U. N. O. SPECIFIC QUALITIES OF IMPROVING THE PEDAGOGICAL MECHANISMS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE ENGINEERS //INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE" INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION". – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 3. – C. 14-18.